

More on the spotted jumping spider *Thyene coccineovittata* (Simon, 1886) in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

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Abstract: The spotted jumping spider *Thyene coccineovittata* (Simon, 1886) has a wide distribution in Africa and is known from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. The species was also accidentally introduced in France and Brazil. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thyene* Simon, 1886 is represented by 52 species and subspecies, with 14 species recorded from South Africa. Most of the *Thyene* species can be distinguished by their colouration and the presence of tufts of long black hairs near the posterior median eyes.

Thyene coccineovittata (Simon, 1886) is a species of African origin described from Senegal as *Hyllus coccineovittatus*. The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa and is known from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. The species was also accidentally introduced in France (Oger & Van Keer, 2017) and Brazil (Mariante & Hill, 2018).

The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa, with notes on their agrobiont status.

TAXONOMY

Thyene coccineovittata (Simon, 1886)

Hyllus coccineovittatus Simon, 1886: 348.

Thyene crudelis: Peckham & Peckham, 1903: 229; Berland & Millot, 1941: 371.

Thyene coccineovittata: Berland & Millot, 1941: 371, 373; Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009: 83.

Diagnostic characteristics: The species was redescribed by Wesolowska and Haddad (2009) with detailed drawings. The live male can be recognised by the rounded reddish-brown carapace, with darker margins and eyes surrounded by black rings and short whitish setae forming poorly contrasted bands: one on middle of thoracic part and two on carapace sides, near the eye field; tufts of long brown bristles form 'horns' at posterior median eyes. The abdomen dark, brownish-fawn, with lighter shiny streak along middle; two pairs of very small, but clearly contrasted white marks posteriorly; venter dark, with two lines composed of white dots (Figs 4–6). Male palp with tibial apophysis very short, tegulum rounded, embolus very long, encircling the tegulum five times (Figs 7–9).

Female: smaller than male; carapace orange-brownish, eye field tinged with grey, eyes circled by black; around anterior median eyes row of white scales; sparse brown and white setae on carapace, tufts of long bristles near posterior median eyes. Abdomen with several lines anteriorly, in posterior two-thirds of its length with three pairs of large blackish patches (Figs 1–3). Legs dark yellow, with brown hairs and spines; first legs thickest, femora I and II thin black stripes on anterolateral side; tibiae short and slightly swollen; metatarsi short; first tibia with three pairs of ventral spines, metatarsus with two pairs; pedipalps pale. Female epigyne typical for *Thyene*, weakly sclerotised, with rectangular depression anteriorly (Figs 10–11).

Figures 1–3. *Thyene coccineovittata* female. Photo credits: 1–2. Peter Webb. 3. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009).

Figures 4–6. *Thyene coccineovittata* male. Photo credits: 4. Vida vd Walt. 5. Peter Webb. 6. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Mali, Senegal, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, South Africa. Introduced to France and Brazil.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Keurkloof district, Ferndale Farm (-33.68, 24.83); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.17, 26.50). **Free State:** Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Greytown (-29.05, 30.60); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngotsche district, Vergeval Farm (-27.35, 31.61); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Maasroom (-22.75, 28.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Swadini Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.2, 30.34). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-32.02, 31.08); Marble Hall (-25.09, 29.09); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal Farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood Farm (-29.87, 30.98); Schagen (-25.43, 30.80); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** Citrusdal (-32.59, 19.02); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37).

Figures 7–11: *Thyene coccineovittata*. 7–9 Male palp. 10–11. Epigyne. Credits: 8, 9, 11. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2009). 7 & 10. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Figure 12. Known distribution of *Thyene coccineovittata* in South Africa.

LIFE STYLE

Thyene coccineovittata is commonly found on vegetation and sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), and Thicket biomes.

The species was identified as an agrobiont species after it was collected from several agroecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) such as avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1998), macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001), and grapefruit orchards in South Africa.

In the macadamia orchards spiders were collected over a 12-month period (July 1997–June 1998) from three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa using dichlorvos as a knock-down spray (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001). Of the 2 778 spiders collected, 2020, 73% belonged to the Salticidae represented by 17 species with *T. coccineovittata* the most abundant species. It represented 30% of all the spiders collected.

Figure 13. Seasonal fluctuation of *Thyene coccineovittata* in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld, South Africa (After Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001).

Males, females, and juveniles were collected throughout the year in roughly comparable numbers, viz. females (32%) males (29%), and juveniles (39%) (Fig. 13). The males peaked in September and February. The number of males declined to a low in May and June and females in July. The most juveniles were recorded in April.

In the avocado orchards *T. coccineovittata* were present in lower numbers with Salticidae representing 31% of all specimens collected. The 426 *T. coccineovittata* sampled represented 11.6% of the total salticid sampled.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from several protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003), and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

In Brazil, *T. coccineovittata* was recorded mainly in urban vegetation (Mariane & Hill, 2018). This may indicate that the species prefers environments such as gardens, urban parks, woods, and forests in Brazil. If the species starts to occupy natural niches, it could pose a threat to arthropod populations and their ecosystem relationships. However, more studies are needed on its invasive potential and its impact on ecosystems.

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